

Structural and spectroscopic aspects of 2,3-butanedionemonoxime-monohydrazone : Theory and experiment

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Abstract : 2,3-Butanedionemonoxime-monohydrazone (BDMMH) (1), a 1 : 1 Schiff base condensate of 2,3-butanedionemonoxime with hydrazine hydrate, was synthesized in methanol. Compound 1 has been characterized by C, H and N microanalyses, FT-IR, ¹H NMR and UV-Vis spectra. The solid state structure of it has been determined through X-ray crystallography. The compound crystallizes in the monoclinic space group with $a = 6.440(4)$, $b = 4.256(3)$, $c = 10.703(7)$ Å, $\beta = 94.102(7)$, $V = 292.6(3)$ Å³ and $Z = 2$. The compound is in the *syn*-methyl and *syn*-methyl conformation. Calculations at the level of Density Functional Theory (DFT) were also performed to corroborate the solid state structure. Computed IR spectrum of 1 was compared with the experimental values. A Molecular Orbital (MO) level of analysis was also undertaken to substantiate the UV-Vis spectral findings. ¹H NMR chemical shifts of 1 in the TMS scale in CDCl₃ is in satisfactory harmony with the calculated chemical shifts based on Gauge-Independent Atomic Orbital (GIAO) approach.

Keywords : Schiff base, oxime, X-ray crystal structure, DFT calculations.

Introduction

The chemistry of oxime, an acronym of oxy-imine, is really vast¹⁻⁵. Oximes are derived from the replacement of the aldehydic or ketonic oxygen atom. This oxime moiety is amphoteric in nature due to the presence of mild basic nitrogen and acidic hydroxyl group. Thus the mode and ability of an oxime moiety to bind metal centers is varied so much so that the coordination chemistry based on oxime-based ligands is vast indeed⁶⁻¹⁰. Again the mode of coordination of an oxime is greatly influenced by the presence of other ancillary group(s) present in an oxime-based ligand. As a ligand, the oxime moiety is potentially ambidentate² and can coordinate either through the nitrogen or oxygen atom. Oxime-based ligands are potential analytical reagents also¹¹. In solid state, oximes show different isomeric forms. Historically isomerism in oxime was first propounded by Werner¹². Due

to hindered rotation around the double bond, oxime can display geometrical isomerism. In this way monoximes have two (*syn* and *anti*) isomeric forms¹³. This number is three (*E,E*; *E,Z* and *Z,Z*) for a dioxime¹⁴. In the solid state free oximes usually are associated through O-H...N hydrogen bonding. In this perspective an aliphatic monoxime, 2,3 butanedionemonoxime and its monohydrazone derivative, 2,3-butanedionemonoxime-monohydrazone (BDMMH) seems to be promising^{15,16}. Ablov and Belichuk studied the coordination chemistry of 1-hydrazone-2-oximes like 2,3-butanedionemonoxime-monohydrazone as early as in 1962¹⁷. Only their 1 : 1 complexes with copper(II) chloride and copper(II) bromide were reported without any structural characterization. Later on in 2000, Datta *et al.* fleshed out the copper(II) chemistry of it further¹⁵. In their report a homoleptic and neutral copper(I) as well as a cationic hexanuclear

copper(II) compounds of BDMMH can be seen. However no structural aspects of any of those compounds emerge therein. Prior to that in 1997, a Ru^{III} compound of BDMMH as such had been reported¹⁸. This also lacks in X-ray crystal structure. Curiously till now even no crystal structure of BDMMH as such is available in the literature. Herein we report the synthesis, characterization and solid state structure of BDMMH for the first time, vis-à-vis a combined experimental and theoretical study on molecular structure, vibrational spectra, ¹H NMR spectra and UV spectral analysis of BDMMH was also undertaken to delve into its structure and spectroscopic properties.

Experimental

All chemicals were of analytical reagent grade and used without further purification. Reagent grade 2,3-butanedionemonoxime, 98% was procured from Sigma-Aldrich and was used without any further purification. Hydrazine hydrate, 80% was purchased from Loba Chemie Pvt. Ltd., India.

Physical measurements :

The melting point was determined by an electro-thermal digital melting point apparatus (SUMSIM, India) and is uncorrected. C, H and N microanalyses were performed by a Perkin-Elmer 2400II elemental analyser. FT-IR spectra (KBr disc) were recorded in the range 4000–400 cm⁻¹ on a Shimadzu FTIR-8400S spectrophotometer. UV-Vis spectra (in MeOH) were recorded on a Shimadzu UV-160A spectrophotometer, 300 MHz ¹H NMR spectrum (in CDCl₃ : reference, TMS) on a Bruker DPX300 spectrometer.

Single crystals suitable for X-ray crystallographic analysis were selected following examination under a microscope. Intensity data were collected at 298(2) K for **1** on a Bruker Smart Apex II diffractometer equipped with 1 K CCD instrument by using a graphite monochromator utilizing MoK_α radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$). Cell parameters were determined using SMART software¹⁹. Data reduction and corrections were performed using SAINTPlus¹⁹. Absorption corrections were made via SADABAS²⁰. The structures were solved by direct methods with the program SHELXS-97 and refined by full-matrix least-squares methods on all F^2 data with SHELXL-

97²¹. It shows a spurious inversion centre in the molecule because of close electron densities between atoms O1 and N2. Thus, both atoms show disorder with half occupancies at the same site. The non-H atoms were refined anisotropically. Hydrogen atoms attached with C1 atoms were added theoretically and treated as riding on the concerned atoms. Hydrogen atoms attached disordered O1 and N2 atoms were located from difference Fourier maps and their global U_{iso} values were refined. The O–H and N–H distances are in the range 0.822 ~ 0.905 Å. After several cycles, these H atoms were constrained to ride on their parent atoms, with $U_{\text{iso}}(\text{H}) = 1.5 U_{\text{eq}}(\text{O and N})$. The final cycle of full-matrix least-squares refinement was based on observed reflections and variable parameters. A summary of data collection, structure refinement for **1** is given in Table 1. Selected bond lengths, bond angles and hydrogen-bond geometry are given respectively in Tables 2 and 3.

Table 1. Crystal data and structure refinement for **1**

CCDC No.	831796
Empirical formula	C ₄ H ₉ N ₃ O
Color/shape	Colorless/needle-shaped
Formula weight	115.14
Temperature (K)	298 (2)
Wavelength (Å)	0.71073
Crystal system	Monoclinic
Crystal size (mm)	0.10 × 0.03 × 0.03
Space group	$P2_1/n$
Unit cell dimensions :	
<i>a</i> (Å)	6.440(4)
<i>b</i> (Å)	4.256(3)
<i>c</i> (Å)	10.703(7)
α (°)	90.000
β (°)	94.102(7)
γ (°)	90.000
Volume (Å ³)	292.6(3)
<i>Z</i>	2
Calculated density (mg m ⁻³)	1.307
Absorption coefficient (mm ⁻¹)	0.098
<i>F</i> (000)	124
θ range for data collection (°)	3.58 < θ < 21.44
Index ranges	-6 < <i>h</i> < 6; -4 < <i>k</i> < 4; -10 < <i>l</i> < 9
Reflections collected	1314
Independent reflections	329 [$R_{\text{int}} = 0.0254$]

Table-1 (contd.)

Completeness to $\theta = 21.44$	99.4%
Absorption correction	Semi-empirical from equivalents
Max. and min. transmission	0.9971 and 0.9903
Refinement method	Full-matrix least-squares on F^2
Data/restraints/parameters	329/0/38
Goodness-of-fit on F^2	1.149
Final R indices [$I > 2\sigma(I)$]	$R_1 = 0.0446$, $wR_2 = 0.1209$
R indices (all data)	$R_1 = 0.0479$, $wR_2 = 0.1241$
Largest diff. peak and hole	0.153 and -0.130 e \AA^{-3}

Table 2. Selected bond lengths (\AA) and angles ($^\circ$) for **1**

C1-C2	1.498(4)	C2-N1	1.290(4)
C1-H1A	0.9600	C2-C2 ⁱ	1.463(6)
N1-N2	1.410(3)	N2-H2A	0.9039
O1-H1	0.8222	N2-H2B	0.9054
N1-O1	1.410(3)		
C2-C1-H1A	109.5	H1A-C1-H1B	109.5
N1-C2-C2 ⁱ	116.4(3)	N1-C2-C1	122.9(3)
C2 ⁱ -C2-C1	120.7(3)	C2-N1-N2	114.6(2)
N1-N2-H2A	120.7	H2A-N2-H2B	119.0
N1-O1-H1	110.2	H2B-N2-H1	129.2
C2-N1-O1	114.6(2)		

Symmetry code : $i - x + 1, -y, -z + 1$ Table 3. Hydrogen-bond geometry (\AA , $^\circ$) for **1**

D-H...A	d(D-H)	d(H...A)	d(D...A)	\angle D-H...A
O1-H1...N1 ⁱⁱ	0.82	2.22	3.025(3)	167.1
N2-H2A...N1 ⁱⁱ	0.90	2.19	3.025(3)	152.6

Symmetry code : $ii - x + 1/2, y + 1/2, -z + 1/2$

2,3-Butanedionemonoxime-monohydrazone (BDMMH) (1) :

2,3-Butanedionemonoxime (10 g, 0.1 mol) was dissolved in 20 mL of methanol. A small amount of insoluble material was removed by filtration. To the yellowish filtrate, hydrazine hydrate (5.5 mL, 0.11 mol) was added dropwise with stirring. The reaction is highly exothermic. The resulting hot orange solution, from which needle shaped crystals started separating within 5 min, was left in the air at room temperature to undergo slow evaporation for 2 h. The crystalline product that deposited was collected by filtration, washed with small portions of chilled methanol and diethyl ether and subsequently dried in air. Yield 8.0 g (70%), m.p. 130–135 $^\circ\text{C}$ (lit. 138 $^\circ\text{C}$)²². The compound is soluble in methanol,

chloroform and dichloromethane (Found : C, 41.89; H, 7.83; N, 35.87. Calcd. for $\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{N}_3\text{O}$: C, 41.71; H, 7.88; N, 36.50%); FT-IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : ν 3391 br(OH), 3231 br(NH), 1641 s(C=N), 1152 s(N-O); UV-Vis (CH_3OH) : λ_{max} ($\epsilon/\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$) 250 nm (13951) and 233 nm (12222); ^1H NMR (δ , CDCl_3) : 11.61 (1H, s, oximato proton), 5.43 (2H, s, NH_2 proton), 2.12 (3H, s, methyl protons adjacent to the hydrazone imine linkage) and 1.89 (3H, s, methyl protons adjacent to the oxime linkage) ppm.

Single crystals suitable for X-ray crystallography were grown by slow evaporation of a moderately concentrated methanolic solution of the compound in a refrigerator in the course of its purification.

Theoretical methods :

The optimization of the compound BDMMH from the experimental structures was carried out with DFT method. B3LYP (Becke's three parameter hybrid functional using the LYP correlation functional) at 6-311G(d) basis set using the Berny method^{23,24} was performed with the Gaussian 03 software package²⁵, and Gauss view visualization program²⁶ to conduct the DFT calculations. B3LYP methods at 6-311G(d) calculation level were employed in investigation of the optimized molecular structures, vibrational frequencies, UV-Vis spectra, ^1H NMR spectra, the frontier orbitals of the 2,3-butanedionemonoxime-monohydrazone. Time-dependent density functional theory (TD-DFT)²⁷⁻²⁹ was used in electronic absorption spectra calculations of the optimized structure. Also, it was calculated in methanol using the Polarizable Continuum Model (PCM)³⁰⁻³³. The vibrational frequencies for this species were scaled by 0.9672³⁴. The vibrational bands were assigned by using Gauss-View molecular visualization program. ^1H NMR chemical shifts were calculated. Standard GIAO/B3LYP/6-311G(d) (Gauge-Independent Atomic Orbital) approach^{35,36} applying B3LYP with 6-311G(d) basic set was used for these calculations. The ^1H NMR chemical shifts are converted into the TMS scale by subtracting the calculated absolute chemical shielding of TMS ($\delta = \Sigma_0 - \Sigma$), where δ is the chemical shift, Σ is the absolute shielding and Σ_0 is the absolute shielding of TMS, whose value is 32.2899 ppm for B3LYP/6-311G(d).

Results and discussion

The solid state structure of the title compound was established through X-ray crystallography. The molecular structure and the atom labeling scheme for **1** is shown in Fig. 1. The hydrogen-bond networks with a $R_4^4(18)$ hydrogen-bonded ring and a $C_2^2(6)$ hydrogen-bonded chain

Fig. 1. 2,3-Butanedionemonoxime-monohydrazone (BDMMH) with ellipsoids at 50% probability level. O1 and N2 share the same site with half occupancies because of their disorder. Disordered N2 and O1A are omitted for clarity. Symmetry code : A $1 - x, -y, 1 - z$.

of the tetrameric unit for **1** is shown in Fig. 2. Selected metrical parameters for this structure are summarized in Table 2. The compound crystallizes in the monoclinic space group with two molecular weight units accommodated per unit cell. The C2-N1 and N1-O1 bond distances of the oxime function in **1** are of values 1.290(4) and 1.410(3) Å, respectively. Similar magnitudes of C-N

and N-O bond distances, 1.290(6) and 1.397(5) Å respectively, for an oxime moiety can be found in 1-phenyl-1- $\{N(4)$ -methylthiosemicarbazone $\}$ -2-oximepropane (H_2Po4M)³⁷. The crystal structure of H_2Po4M was found to have the oxime and thiosemicarbazone moieties on the opposite sides of the carbon-carbon backbone. This relative dispositions of the functionalities as found in H_2Po4M is akin to our case. In **1**, the oxime and the hydrazone moieties are on the opposite sides of the C2-C2A bond (Symmetry code : A $-x+1, -y, -z+1$). The C2-N1-O1 angle of the oxime function is 114.6(2)°. The magnitude of the torsion angle around C2A-C2 seems to be very informative.

The torsion angle of C-C=N-O close to 0° corresponds to the *cis* configuration; while it is of 180° for a *trans* configuration of the oxime function with respect to the C-C connectivity. In **1**, the C2A-C2-N1-O1 torsion angle is of 179.8(3)° as found from X-ray crystallography (Table 4). This value is close to 180°. Thus the oxime group in **1** adopts a clear *trans*-planar arrangement with respect to C2A-C2 linkage. Again, the torsion angle, C2-N1-O1-H1 is 174.4(4)°. The O-H bond may be *syn-planar* or *anti-periplanar* to C=N. Though *anti-periplanar* conformation is common, a few cases are also known where the *syn-planar* situation (torsion angle close to 0°) are also known³⁸. This difference in conformation arises due to the rotation around the C-C single bond, the connector in a heterodiene system. In our case this connector is the C2A-C2 bond. This bond length is of 1.463(6)Å, a value considerably shorter than the theoretical C(sp²)-

Fig. 2. A molecular packing diagram of BDMMH (**1**) forming H-bonds : (a) the $R_4^4(18)$ hydrogen-bonded ring shown in the tetrameric unit and $C_2^2(6)$ zigzag chain, dotted lines for H-bonds.

Table 4. Torsion angles ($^{\circ}$) for **1**

C2 ⁱ -C2-N1-N2	179.8(3)
C1-C2-N1-N2	0.2(4)
C2-N1-O1-H1	174.4(4)
Symmetry codes : $i - x + 1, -y, -z + 1$	

C(sp²) single-bond (1.48 Å). For oximes having co-planar conjugated double bonds, this bond length lies in the range of 1.47–1.50 Å³⁹. Thus the shrinkage of the C2A-C2 bond length in **1** from the ideal C-C single bond length may be due to the development of a partial double bond character in it due to a delocalization in this heterodiene system.

In a monoxime having two double bonds (inclusive of the oxime moiety), three possible isomers are possible — *syn,syn* ; *syn,anti* and *anti,anti*. **1** have two such centres owing to the presence of the C2=N1 and C2A=N1A double bonds. With respect to these, **1** is the *syn*-methyl and *syn*-methyl isomer as found in its solid state structure (Fig. 3). This type of *syn*-methyl and *syn*-methyl isomeric form is present in other monoxime also⁴⁰. *Anti*-methyl and *anti*-acetyl isomer is, however, also known in a monoxime⁴⁰.

Fig. 3 Possible isomers of **1**.

The O-H \cdots N hydrogen bond in **1** (Fig. 2b) with donor, O-H (0.82 Å) and acceptor, H \cdots N (2.22 Å) have been detected from X-ray crystallography (Table 3). Though the position of the H atom as deciphered from X-ray crystallography is calculated (through the riding model), it seems that the H atom of the O-H \cdots N hydro-

gen bond in **1** is closer to the O center by a value of 0.7 Å from the baricentre of the O-N distance (3.025 Å). There are only a few examples of X-ray crystal structures with O-H \cdots N bonds in which the H atom has at least similar distances to O and N. There the O-H and H \cdots N distances are of 1.23 and 1.29 Å respectively^{41,42}. However the first O-H \cdots N hydrogen bond with a centered proton as detected by Neutron Diffraction (ND) at 20 K has shown the O \cdots N distance is of 2.506 Å⁴³. To date this is the shortest known O-H \cdots N hydrogen bond for which ND data have been available. In our case this O-H \cdots N distance is of 3.025 Å, a value significantly larger than 2.506 Å. Thus based on this distance criterion alone the O-H \cdots N hydrogen bond in **1** is weak indeed.

IR spectra :

The FT-IR spectrum of the title Schiff base (**1**) was recorded in 4000–400 cm⁻¹ frequency region in the solid state using the KBr disc technique. Selected bands of diagnostic importance are collected in Table 6.

The spectrum of **1** due to OH group displays somewhat broadened bands within 3391 cm⁻¹ region. The OH group gives rise to three vibrations namely stretching, in-plane and out-of plane bending vibrations. The OH group vibrations are susceptible to environment. Often they show considerable shifting in a hydrogen bonded species⁴⁴. The hydroxyl stretching band is generally observed around 3500 cm⁻¹. It is pertinent to note that for unsubstituted phenol, the hydroxyl stretching vibration appears in the gas phase at 3657 cm⁻¹⁴⁵. The band due to the free hydroxyl group is generally sharp with a strong intensity. However, for solid, liquid and concentrated solution a broad band with diminished intensity for OH group is noticed⁴⁶. In our case the medium intensity band discernable at 3391 cm⁻¹ is assigned as the stretching OH vibration. A comparison of this band at 3391 cm⁻¹ in **1** with that of the computed value at 3397 cm⁻¹ shows a marginal positive deviation by 6 cm⁻¹. This is due to the strong intermolecular hydrogen bonding as evidenced from the solid state structure of **1** (Fig. 2).

The OH in-plane bending vibration generally appears at 1150–1250 cm⁻¹ and is not much affected due to hydrogen bonding unlike the stretching and out-of-plane bending vibrations⁴⁷. The in-plane bending vibration for the OH group is observed at 1152 cm⁻¹ in the FT-IR

Table 5. Some selected experimental and calculated bond lengths (Å) and bond angles (°) for **1**

Experimental bonds	Computed bonds	Experimental bond length	Syn	Anti	4-merci Axial	4-merci Equatorial	4-merci pcm Axial	4-merci pcm Equatorial
C1-C2	C8-C4	1.498(4)	1.5066	1.5034	1.5028	1.5003	1.5035	1.5032
C2-N1	C4-N5	1.290(4)	1.2834	1.2883	1.2878	1.2902	1.2882	1.2916
O1-H1	O6-H3	0.8222	0.9634	0.9636	0.9852	0.9856	0.9868	0.987
C1-H1A	C8-H7	0.9600	1.0888	1.0858	1.0941	1.0857	1.088	1.0855
C2-C2 ⁱ	C3-C4	1.463(6)	1.4866	1.4776	1.4765	1.4769	1.4781	1.477
N1-N2	N1-N2	1.410(3)	1.3707	1.3638	1.3778	1.3643	1.3755	1.3614
N2-H2A	N1-H1	0.9039	1.0173	1.0103	1.0165	1.0092	1.0164	1.01
N2-H2B	N2-H2B	0.9054	1.0107	1.0168	1.0121	1.0159	1.012	1.016
N1-O1	N5-O6	1.410(3)	1.4098	1.4038	1.3836	1.3911	1.3871	1.3944
C2-C1-H1A	C4-C8-H9	109.5	110.879	109.899	109.72	110.084	109.703	110.073
H1A-C1-H1B	H9-C8-H7	109.5	109.031	109.773	108.22	109.944	109.829	109.864
N1-C2-C2 ⁱ	N5-C4-C3	116.4(3)	116.722	120.856	115.174	117.36	115.363	117.553
N1-C2-C1	N2-C3-C7	122.9(3)	116.536	123.208	122.42	123.381	122.494	123.314
C2 ⁱ -C2-C1	C3-C4-C8	120.7(3)	119.868	120.856	120.574	120.526	120.875	120.525
C2-N1-N2	C3-N1-N2	114.6(2)	118.375	118.682	118.767	118.766	118.943	119.055
N1-O1-H1	N5-O6-H3	110.2	102.486	102.663	103.021	105.797	103.329	106.24
H2B-N2-H1	H1-N1-H2	129.2	111.393	112.019	111.274	112.397	110.959	112.059
C2-N1-O1	C4-N5-O6	114.6(2)	111.39	111.742	113.742	112.086	113.434	112.081
C2 ⁱ -C2-N1-N2	C4-C3-N2-N1	179.8(3)	4.02	5.012	178.606	1.145	177.98	0.844
C1-C2-N1-N2	C7-C3-N2-N1	0.2(4)	3.126	2.424	177.866	0.182	177.553	0.351

Symmetry code : $i - x + 1, -y, -z + 1$ **Table 6.** Some selected experimental and calculated IR frequencies for **1** with assignments

Experimental wavenumber (cm ⁻¹)	Calculated wavenumber (cm ⁻¹)	Band assignment
3391	3397	$\nu_{as}(\text{OH})$ Oxime
1152	1181	$\nu_s(\text{OH})$ Oxime
681	660	$\delta(\text{O-H})$ Oxime
1641	1638	$\nu(\text{CN})$
1574	1526	$\nu(\text{CN})$ Oxime

spectrum of **1** with a medium intensity. The theoretically computed wavenumber at 1181 cm⁻¹ is in satisfactory agreement with this observed data.

The O-H out-of-plane deformation vibration for phenol lies in the region 290–320 cm⁻¹ for free O-H and in the region 517–710 cm⁻¹ for associated O-H⁴⁸. In both inter- and intra-molecular association, however, this is shifted to higher wavenumber. This shift in wavenumber (energy) is in direct proportion with the strength of the underlying hydrogen bond, since an increased amount of

energy is needed to twist a hydrogen bond. Earlier such a situation was realized also⁴⁹. The theoretically computed wavenumber at 660 cm⁻¹ is in fair agreement with the experimentally obtained wavenumber at 681 cm⁻¹. Band observed at 3231 cm⁻¹ is tentatively assigned to $\nu(\text{NH})$ for compound **1**.

The C=N stretching skeletal bands are observed in the frequency region of 1650–1550 cm⁻¹⁵⁰. The position of this band is a function of molecular structure. For ready reckoning, we may cite that for a thiosemicarbazone ligand, earlier this $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ vibration was reported at 1571–1602 cm⁻¹⁵¹; while this is of 1606–1627 cm⁻¹ for a benzophenone substituted semicarbazone⁵². Our experimentally obtained value (1641 cm⁻¹) for $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ corroborates those observations. The theoretically evaluated value of 1638 cm⁻¹ for $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ matches with this. The sharp, medium intensity band at 1574 cm⁻¹ is attributed to the C=N (oxime linkage) mode⁵³. The computed wavenumber for this is assigned at 1526 cm⁻¹. Thus the experimental FT-IR of **1** fairly matches with the calculated values.

UV spectral analysis :

The UV-Vis absorption spectra of **1** was measured in methanol. The bands are obtained mainly in the UV region with high extinction coefficients. The data are tabulated in Table 7. On the basis of the fully optimized ground state structure, TD-DFT/B3LYP/6-311G(d,p) calculations have been undertaken to determine the low-lying excited

Table 7. Selected experimental and calculated UV bands for **1**

Experimental (nm)	Calculated (nm)	Oscillator strength (ϵ)
250	243	0.3750
233	236	0.2566
233	231	0.1557

states of **1**. The calculated parameters thus obtained are the vertical excitation energies, oscillator strength (f) and wavelength of transitions. According to the Frank-Condon principle the maximum absorption intensity (λ_{\max}) of a band in an electronic transition (UV-Vis spectrum) corresponds to vertical transition. The molecular orbitals participating in such transitions are the highest occupied molecular orbitals (HOMOs) and the lowest unoccupied molecular orbitals (LUMOs). The HOMO, an electron donor, represents the ability to donate electron; while the LUMO, an electron receptor, represents the efficacy to receive electron. The HOMO and LUMO in **1** as computed by us is shown in Fig. 4. The HOMO in **1** is located primarily over the two centrally aligned units of the tetrameric unit. However, the LUMO as deciphered from computation, hovers mainly over the two terminally located units of the tetrameric form of **1**. The difference in energy between the HOMO and LUMO, the energy gap, is a measure of the stability of the two underlying orbitals so involved in electronic transition. This energy gap also

dictates the stability/topology of the structure. Appearance of two experimental charge transfer (CT) bands at 250 and 233 nm in methanol in the UV spectrum of **1** is suggestive of its potential non-linearity. Again, as the HOMO-LUMO transition takes place in the UV region, close to but out of the visible zone, it can be predicted that this molecule will be colorless or slightly colored. In this connection, it can be noted that the colour of the freshly prepared **1** is white which turns to light yellow on prolonged exposure in the air. The calculated wavelengths of these CT bands are discernable at 243 and 231 nm.

NMR analysis :

The ^1H nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) chemical shifts of the molecule, **1** were calculated by the Gauge Independent Atomic Orbital (GIAO) method^{35,36} and compared with the experimental results. The isotropic chemical shifts (ICS) are often used in the identification of reactive organic species. This is of much help for an ionic species also. It is pertinent to note that accurate prediction of molecular geometry is a prerequisite for the reliable calculation of magnetic parameters like NMR chemical shifts. Thus full geometry optimization of **1** was performed by using the standard method. Then, Gauge Independent Atomic Orbital (GIAO) ^1H chemical shifts of **1** were calculated on it. The chemical shifts so calculated were converted into the TMS scale by employing the relation, $\delta = \Sigma - \Sigma_0$, where δ is the chemical shift, Σ is the absolute shielding and Σ_0 is the absolute shielding of TMS. The value of Σ_0 is 32.2899 ppm for B3LYP/6-311G(d). The observed ^1H chemical shifts in CDCl_3 for **1** are in good agreement with the computed values (Table 8).

Fig. 4 Pictures of 4-mer LUMO (left) and HOMO (right) in **1**.

Table 8. The calculated and observed ^1H NMR chemical shifts for **1** in the TMS scale

Types of proton	Absolute shielding, Σ in ppm	Chemical shift, δ in ppm in the TMS scale	Theoretical average chemical shift, $\langle \delta \rangle$ in ppm	Experimental chemical shift, in ppm
Oximato proton	20.643	11.65	11.61	11.61
Hydrazone protons	26.692	5.997	5.34	5.43
	27.594	4.696		
Methyl protons adjacent to hydrazone moiety	30.637	1.653	2.22	2.12
	30.609	1.681		
Methyl protons adjacent to oximato moiety	28.951	3.339	2.18	1.89
	30.163	2.127		
	30.146	2.144		
	29.595	2.695		

Concluding remarks :

The title compound, 2,3-butanedionemonoxime-monohydrazone (BDMMH) has been synthesized and characterized by C, H and N microanalyses, ^1H NMR, FT-IR, UV-Vis and single-crystal X-ray diffraction. The solid state structure reveals that the compound is in *syn*-methyl and *syn*-methyl conformation. The optimized geometrical parameters, vibrational frequencies, chemical shift values and the electronic properties like absorption wavelengths have been calculated by B3LYP/6-311G(d) basis set. The experimental and calculated results are in a good harmony.

Supplementary material :

The cif file of **1** was deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Center (CCDC 831796). The data can be obtained free of charge from the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Center, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1EZ, UK; Fax : 44-1223-336-033; E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk.

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References

1. P. Chaudhuri, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2003, **243**, 143.
2. A. Chakravorty, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1974, **13**, 1.
3. P. K. Nanda, M. Bera, A. M. da Costa Ferreira, A. Paduan-Filho and D. Ray, *Polyhedron*, 2009, **28**, 4065.
4. O. Das, N. N. Adarsh, A. Paul and T. K. Paine, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2010, **49**, 541.
5. R. Ruiz, J. Sanz, F. Lloret, M. Julve, J. Faus, C. Bois and M. C. Munoz, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1993, **20**, 3035.
6. J. P. Naskar, C. Biswas, B. Guhathakurta, N. Aliaga-Alcalde, L. Lu and M. Zhu, *Polyhedron*, 2011, **30**, 2310.
7. T. C. Stamatatos, J. C. Vlahopoulou, Y. Sanakis, C. P. Raptopoulou, V. Psycharis, A. K. Boudalis and S. P. Perlepes, *Inorg. Chem. Commun.*, 2006, **9**, 814.
8. J. P. Naskar, C. Biswas, L. Lu and M. Zhu, *J. Chem. Crystallogr.*, 2011, **41**, 502.
9. T. C. Stamatatos, A. Escuer, K. A. Abboud, C. P. Raptopoulou, S. P. Perlepes and G. Christou, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2008, **47**, 11825 and references cited therein.
10. V. Y. Kukushkin and A. J. L. Pombeiro, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1999, **181**, 147.
11. R. B. Singh, B. S. Garg and R. P. Singh, *Talanta*, 1979, **26**, 425.
12. A. Hantzsch and A. Werner, *Chem. Ber.*, 1890, **23**, 1.
13. G. B. Kauffman, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1966, **43**, 155.
14. D. Manniera and W. Haerdi, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1958, **41**, 205.
15. P. Chakrabarti, V. G. Puranik, J. P. Naskar, S. Hati and D. Datta, *Indian. J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2000, **39**, 571.
16. A. Audhya, M. Maity, K. Bhattacharya, R. Clérac and M. Chaudhury, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2010, **49**, 9026.
17. A. V. Ablov and N. I. Belichuk, *Russ. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, **7**, 401.

18. Abd El-Mottaleb M. Ramadan, Ibrahim M. El-Mehasseb and Raaft M. Issa, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 1997, **22**, 529.
19. Bruker (2000). SMART (Version 5.0) and SAINT (Version 6.02). Bruker AXS Inc., Madison, Wisconsin, USA.
20. G. M. Sheldrick, (2000) SADABAS. University of Göttingen, Germany.
21. G. M. Sheldrick, *Acta Crystallogr.*, 2008, **A64**, 112.
22. A. Darapsky and H. Spannagel, *J. Fuer Prakt. Chemie. (Leipzig)*, 1915, [2] **92**, 272.
23. C. Peng, P. Y. Ayala, H. B. Schlegel and M. J. Frisch, *J. Comput. Chem.*, 1996, **17**, 49.
24. P. J. Stephens, F. J. Devlin, C. F. Chabrowski and M. J. Frisch, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1994, **98** 11623.
25. M. J. Frisch, G. W. Trucks, H. B. Schlegel, G. E. Scuseria, M. A. Robb, J. R. Cheeseman, J. A. Montgomery (Jr.), J. T. Vreven, K. N. Kudin, J. C. Burant, J. M. Millam, S. S. Iyengar, J. Tomasi, V. Barone, B. Mennucci, M. Cossi, G. Scalmani, N. Rega, G. A. Petersson, H. Nakatsuji, M. Hada, M. Ehara, K. Toyota, R. Fukuda, J. Hasegawa, M. Ishida, T. Nakajima, Y. Honda, O. Kitao, H. Nakai, M. Klene, X. Li, J. E. Knox, H. P. Hratchian, J. B. Cross, V. Bakken, C. Adamo, J. Jaramillo, R. Gomperts, R. E. Stratmann, O. Yazyev, A. J. Austin, R. Cammi, C. Pomelli, J. W. Ochterski, P. Y. Ayala, K. Morokuma, G. A. Voth, P. Salvador, J. J. Dannenberg, V. G. Zakrzewski, S. Dapprich, A. D. Daniels, M. C. Strain, O. Farkas, D. K. Malick, A. D. Rabuck, K. Raghavachari, J. B. Foresman, J. V. Ortiz, Q. Cui, A. G. Baboul, S. Clifford, J. Cioslowski, B. B. Stefanov, G. Lui, A. Liashenko, P. Piskorz, I. Komaromi, R. L. Martin, D. J. Fox, T. Keith, M. A. Al-Laham, C. Y. Peng, A. Nanayakkara, M. Challacombe, P. M. W. B. Gill, B. Johnson, W. Chen, M. W. Wong, C. Gonzalez and J. A. Pople, GAUSSIAN 03, Revision C.02, Gaussian Inc., Wallingford CT, 2004.
26. A. Frisch, R. D. Dennington II, T. A. Keith, J. Milliam, A. B. Nielsen, A. Holder and J. Hiscocks, GaussView Reference, Version 4.0. Gaussian Inc., Pittsburgh, 2007.
27. E. Runge and E. K. U. Gross, *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 1984, **52**, 997.
28. R. E. Stratmann, G. E. Scuseria and M. J. Frisch, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1998, **109**, 8218.
29. R. Bauernschmitt and R. Ahlrichs, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1996, **256**, 454.
30. S. Miertus, E. Scrocco and J. Tomasi, *Chem. Phys.*, 1981, **55**, 117.
31. V. Barone and M. Cossi, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1998, **A102**, 1995.
32. M. Cossi, N. Rega, G. Scalmani and V. Barone, *J. Comput. Chem.*, 2003, **24**, 669.
33. J. Tomasi, B. Mennucci and R. Cammi, *Chem. Rev.*, 2005, **105**, 2999.
34. J. P. Merrick, D. Moran and L. Radom, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 2007, **A111**, 11683.
35. R. Ditchfield, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1972, **56**, 5688.
36. K. Wolinski, J. F. Hinton and P. Pulay, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1990, **112**, 8251.
37. W. Kaminsky, J. P. Jasinski, R. Woudenberg, K. I. Goldberg and D. X. West, *J. Mol. Struct.*, 2002, **608**, 135.
38. L. Chertanova, C. Pascard and N. Sheremetev, *Acta Cryst.*, 1994, **B50**, 708 and references cited therein.
39. H. Saarinen, J. Korvenranta and E. Näsäkkälä, *Cryst. Str. Commun.*, 1977, **6**, 557.
40. V. Bertolasi and G. Gilli, *Acta Cryst.*, 1982, **B38**, 502.
41. F. Takusagawa, K. Hirotsu and A. Shimada, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1973, **46**, 2292.
42. Z. Malarski, I. Majerz and T. Lis, *J. Mol. Struct.*, 1996, **380**, 249.
43. T. Steiner, I. Majerz and C. C. Wilson, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2001, **40**, 2651.
44. D. Michalska, D. C. Bienko, A. J. A. Bienko and Z. Latajaka, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1996, **100** 1186.
45. S. P. V. Chamundeeswari, E. R. J. J. Samuel and N. Sundaraganesan, *Eur. J. Chem.*, 2011, **2**, 136.
46. J. Marshal, *Indian J. Phys.*, 1998, **72B**, 661.
47. N. Sundaraganesan, H. Saleem and S. Mohan, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 2003, **A59**, 2511.
48. G. Varsanyi, "Assignments for Vibrational Spectra of Seven Hundred Benzene Derivatives", Vol. 1 and 2, Academic Kiado, Budapest, 1973.
49. I. D. Sadekov, *Rus. Chem. Rev.*, 1970, **30**, 179.
50. R. Saxena, L. D. Kandpaul and G. N. Mathur, *Polym. Sci.*, 2002, **A40**, 3951.
51. N. A. Mangalam and M. R. P. Kurup, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 2009, **A71**, 2040.
52. A. A. El-Asmy and G. A. A. Al-Hazmi, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 2009, **A71**, 1885.
53. K. Nakamoto, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds, Part B", 6th ed., John Wiley & Sons, Hoboken, 2009.

